

PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPING OF ECONOMIC COMPETENCES OF TECHNICAL COLLEGE STUDENTS

Khamidova Dilorom Muhitdinovna

Teacher of Koson Agrotechnological College

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8029115>

Abstract. *In this article, the process of developing economic competence in the education of technical school students, increasing their intellectual potential, and forming the ability of technical school students to solve professional problems based on the acquired knowledge, skills and work experience is shown. It requires the creation of favorable opportunities for the effective use of the principles of competence development in solving problems in the development of economic competences of technical school students.*

Keywords: *economic competence, economic knowledge, principle of competence, adaptation, knowledge, skill.*

The process of developing economic competences in the education of technical school students is manifested in the increase of their intellectual potential, the formation of the ability of students to solve professional problems based on the acquired knowledge, skills and work experience. The acquisition of economic knowledge by technical school students requires the creation of favorable opportunities for effective use of the principles of competence development in solving problems.

The research serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan LRU- No.637 of September 23, 2020 “On Education” [1], Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan LRU- No.406 of September 14, 2016 “State policy on youth”.

In the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, it is envisaged to update the content of the continuous education system in terms of quality, improve the teaching methodology, pay attention to the in-depth study of basic subjects, and state education standards. Tasks such as developing criteria for evaluating pedagogical activity based on acquired competencies are defined [3].

Economics is a field that studies and applies methods and tools to create a prosperous life for all members of society. The sole purpose of the economy is to create a better lifestyle for every member of society. Other secondary goals arise from this main goal: ensuring economic development, development of production, employment for all, etc.

Economy is an activity aimed at meeting material and non-material needs of people. Regardless of this activity, it still requires certain material conditions and labor [6].

The word “economy” comes from the Greek word “oikonomos”, which means “one who manages a household”. At first, this scene may seem peculiar. But in fact, households and economies have a lot in common[6].

Theoretical analyzes conducted by many researchers show that in theoretical and pedagogical practice “economic education”, “economic learning” the concepts of “economic culture” and “education in economics” are used [7].

Economic knowledge. It includes concrete and practical components of economic education, as well as the goal-oriented activity of the teacher and the student in the formation of economic literacy. The main components of economic education are the content of economic

education (economic competence), economic literacy, economic knowledge, skills and qualifications, practical experience, competence [7].

Economic education is a mandatory part of education, the main purpose of which is to form the personality of a technical school student, to adapt to market conditions, and to train personnel who can carry out their activities economically.

It is known that the analysis of the results of social and pedagogical surveys in the education of technical school students, the knowledge and skills of increasing economic literacy in the educational process, eliminating this gap in the knowledge of technical school students is differential from the teacher, but individual. shows that it also requires the principle.

In order to expand the logical thinking of the technical school students, to develop their artistic thinking, and to increase the activity of speech related to the economy, it is appropriate to select and recommend competence knowledge from the works of Oriental thinkers, scientists, and poets.

The word competence has different definitions and principles. In particular, the word competence is explained in the “National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan” as follows: competence (lat. *competo* - I am achieving, I am worthy, I am worthy) - the law, charter of a certain state body (local self-government body) or an official or scope of powers, rights and duties defined by another document; knowledge, experience in this or that field. The term "competence" in a broad sense means the ability to apply knowledge and skills based on practical experience and act successfully in solving common problems.

It comes from the Latin word “*campetere*” - to be compatible. “Initiative” competence. Determination: being able to initiate action and effectively influence the event with personal positive aspects. Always be in search, take on new tasks, additional work. A competency-based approach to education guides students to acquire various skills and act effectively in their social, professional, and personal lives in the future.

Competence is a sign of activity that leads to an expected result. It is a product of knowledge and the ability of a specialist to apply it in practice. The difference between competence and knowledge is that it cannot be defined or evaluated without practical performance of the task. Skill is an important criterion of competence, which is manifested as a result of repeated application in various situations, including problem situations. Practical competence is a product of knowledge and the ability to apply it in practice. Also, competence, unlike knowledge, does not appear without practical activity and cannot be assessed. Professional competence is the ability to effectively apply knowledge and skills in practical experience in solving issues related to professional activity.

Based on modern principles, it involves the formation of basic and subject-specific competencies in technical school students through pedagogical mutual integration in the process of teaching technical school students. The principles of including the competence principle in the content of the standards of professional education and general education in the world's leading scientific centers and higher education institutions, their influence on changes in the links of the pedagogical system, psychological and methodological bases and features, independently the concept of achieving educational results, the interpretation of the competence approach, scientific researchers are being carried out on the competences for personal development, social and activity in a certain field [4].

On the basis of scientific approaches aimed at increasing the quality of educational and methodical support of teachers' competence, introduction of virtual forms of practical training, competence approaches in teaching profession-oriented subjects, practical training reflecting interdisciplinary teaching serves to increase the quality and efficiency of education [4].

Education based on the principle of competence is characterized by the preparation of students to use the acquired information in standard and non-standard situations of educational and life activities. Adaptation of school education to the requirements of modern development, improvement of electronic educational resources from subjects, provision of active communication of technical school students with electronic resources, implementation of independent education and self-assessment, operative search for necessary information it implies the formation of competencies to find and use it in solving emerging problems. From this point of view, one of the indicators of the quality of education is competence. It is not only a collection of knowledge and skills, but it is characterized by the ability of technical school students to mobilize the acquired knowledge and apply it in practice in specific situations. The main essence of teaching based on the principle of competence is to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the course of education, which is organized from vocational subjects, in their personal life, as well as in their future professional and social activities. orientation to the formation of acquisition competencies is considered. It is necessary for students to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships during their future life, to take their place in society, to solve the problems encountered in this process, and most importantly, to be competitive in their field and profession. must have basic competencies [3].

Competencies formed in students are divided into three levels: basic competencies; general (subject) competencies; private competencies.

The implementation of the principles in pedagogical practice for the development of economic competences in the education of technical school students is carried out through the following rules.

This justifies the need to clarify the content of education in the training of technical school students and the necessary basis for developing the competence of technical school students and the content of subject-related competencies, to improve the competence of technical school students based on the general principles of competence.

Competencies that prepare the ground for the general development of a student's personality are called basic competences, and competences that are formed only through the subject of study are called special competencies. It is known that through the education and training process, general secondary schools provide students with basic competencies, including communication, information processing, self-development as a person, socially active citizenship, general cultural, mathematical literacy, awareness of science and technology innovations, and formation of use competencies [5].

It was shown that there is a positive relationship between the attitude of technical school students towards the economy and teachers. In addition, the incidence of taking additional economics courses was positively and significantly related to various measures of technical students' attitudes toward the course and teacher grade expectations and grade expectations. Although students' and teachers' perceptions of how well an instructor teaches may differ, they are actually interrelated.

Various teaching methods have been identified that have great potential for teaching technical school students in economics.

- No-limit of teaching technical college students;
- Problem solving in collaboration;
- Working with assignment
- Lecture method;
- Lecture plus;
- Interactive learning.

Studies and experiments have found that the teaching method, which includes several teaching methods for the development of economic competence in teaching technical school students, enhances the long-term retention of the lesson content.

Thus, the principles of the development of economic competence in the training of technical school students are considered as a set of fundamental and professionally oriented components. On the basis of the analysis of educational standards and other regulatory documents, the structural and functional structure of the structure and content of economic competence aimed at the development of competence, organization of practical training, training of technical school students was developed.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2020 yil 23 sentyabrdagi O'RQ-637 sonli "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonuni

2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining 2016 yil 14 sentyabpdagi O‘RQ-406 son “Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to‘g‘risida”gi Qonuni.
3. Qoraev, S. (2016). Specific features of interdisciplinary coherence and interoperability. “Education, Science and Innovation,” 2 (2), 45-50.
4. Barakayevich, Q. S., & Baxtiyorovna, A. S. (2021). Xalqaro dastur talablari asosida innovatsion ta‘lim muhitini yaratish. Integration of science, education and practise. Scientific-methodical journal, 1(02), 132-137.
5. Sulaymonov, J. B. O., Nishonqulov, S. F. O., & Gofurov, M. R. (2021). Geografik axborot tizimlari va amaliy iqtisodiyot: potentsial arizalar va hissalarini dastlabki muhokamalari. Scientific progress, 2(2), 1371-1377.
6. O‘lmasov, A D.Axmedov, B.Xonturayev. “Iqtisodiy bilim asoslari”: O‘quv qo‘llanma - T.: “Iqtisodiyot”, 2020. - 216 b.
7. Solomchenko M.A., Molchanov A.S. Formirovaniye ekonomicheskoy gramotnosti u studentov fakultetov fizicheskoy kulturi i sporta. Fundamentalniye issledovani Y. 2011. № 8-2. C. 307-310.